

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Thermal-Floating Roller Peel Behaviour of Composite-Ti Adhesive Joints for Repair

Presenter: Sridhar Idapalapati, NTU Singapore.

MSridhar@ntu.edu.sg

Dharun Vadugappatty Srinivasan, Atin Aggarwal, Sridhar Idapalapati,

Rolls-Royce@NTU Corporate Lab, Nanyang Technological University Singapore, Singapore-639798.

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Contents

- Introduction
- Problem description
- Debonding technologies
- Methodology
- Materials and manufacturing
- Test results
- Debonding map
- Future work
- Conclusion

Introduction

- Adhesive bonding in hybrid joint components

Image courtesy: GE Aviation

GE9X blade made up of steel alloy bonded with carbon fibre leading edge-structural glass fibre trailing edges.

- Complex aerodynamic shapes
- Negligible assembly weight
- Synergetic effects of multi-materials
- High corrosion resistant
- No holes- no stress concentrations
- Effective load transferring using bonded area

Problem description

- Permanently bonded with high performance epoxy adhesives
- Could not be disassembled in various repair scenarios
- Undamaged high cost composites could not be reused
- Poor product life cycle

- Different damages for a hybrid adhesive joint in service.

1. Metal erosion
2. Severe metal erosion or dent
3. Metal work disbonding
4. Near-surface delamination of composites
5. Sub-surface delamination of composites

- Adhesive
- Carbon composite blade
- Ti-6Al-4V metal work

Debonding Technologies

- Separating the adhesively bonded adherends for repair
- Ensuring no damage to the underlying composites or sub-structures
- Should meet the repair environment conditions, low repair cost
- Different methods: *Thermo-mechanical, Chemical, Electrical and Laser shock waves*
- Selected method for the study: Thermo-mechanical debonding

Effect of time delay of symmetrical laser shock wave on debonding depth in CFRP composites
Meriem Ghrib et. al, Composite Structures, 2017

Failure of epoxy adhesive under electrical stress- A method of electrical debonding

Debonding Technologies: Thermo-mechanical debonding

What?

- Applying thermal energy and mechanical load to debond the composite and metal adherend

Key processing parameters

- Debonding temperature
- Debonding force

Requirements

- knowledge on temperature dependent bulk adhesive behaviour and adhesive joint behaviour
- Optimized KPVs – low repair cost

Risks

- Thermal damage to composites
- Mechanical damage to composites
- Damage to substructures

Methodology

Bulk adhesive behavior

- Glass transition temperature
- Storage and loss modulus
- Tensile properties

Hybrid joint behavior

- Floating roller peel adhesion at different temperatures
- Competing failure mechanisms

Debonding map

- Selecting the optimized temperature for given practical constraints

Materials and Manufacturing

Bulk adhesive specimen for DMA testing

Bulk adhesive dog-bone specimen for tensile testing

All dimensions are in mm

Hybrid adhesive joint for floating roller peel testing

Composite adherend: HexPly M21/37%/7581,
Glass fiber reinforced polymer composite

Metal adherend: Ti-6Al-4V sheet

Adhesive: Epoxy film adhesive, aerospace grade

Surface preparation: Composite- White Alumina grit blasted
Acetone degreased

Ti alloy- White Alumina grit blasted
AC130-2 Solgel treated
EW5005 primer applied

Dynamic mechanical testing of bulk adhesives

Testing parameters

- Testing method: ASTM D5279-13
- Heating rate: 2°C/min
- Dwell time: 10 minutes
- Cooling rate: 30°C/min

Results

- Significant reduction in storage modulus can be seen in the temperature range between $0.75 T_g$ and T_g
- $\tan \delta$ maximum peak value of 0.95 near T_g - High viscous flow

Storage and loss modulus of bulk adhesive as a function of temperature

Tensile testing of bulk adhesives

Testing parameters

- Testing method: ASTM D6318-14
- Temperature : $0.21T_g$ and $0.75 T_g$
- Displacement rate: 1 mm/min

Results

Tensile properties	Temperature (°C)	
	$0.21T_g$	$0.75T_g$
Tensile stress (MPa)	41.4	13.18
Elastic modulus (GPa)	1.42	0.37
Yield stress (MPa) @ 0.2% offset	36.27	7.84
Failure strain (%)	11	>23
Fracture stress (MPa)	39.7	-

Tensile stress vs tensile strain response of bulk adhesive at different temperature

Floating roller peel (FRP) testing of GFRP-Ti alloy joints

- Standard: ASTM D3167
- Displacement rate : 135 mm/min
- Test temperature:
 - $0.21T_g$,
 - $0.75T_g$,
 - T_g ,
 - $1.08T_g$,
 - $1.25T_g$ and
 - $1.33T_g$

Floating roller peel testing of hybrid joints inside a convention thermal chamber

Peel behaviour at $0.21 T_g$

- Very high fingering of adhesives at initial displacement
- Ti-alloy bending creates a compressive region ahead of the fracture surface
- Out-of-plane load initial plies of composites-very critical interlaminar stress
- Delamination of composites occurs and continues in the same plane (weak)
- Change in loading mode lead to crack kinking
- Initial behaviour dominates the average peel behaviour

Inter-laminar failure of composite in the hybrid joint tested at $0.21 T_g$

Peel behaviour at $0.21 T_g$

- Peel fracture energy cannot be considered as critical energy for the adhesion
- The composite adherend plays a major role in low temperature peel behavior

Failure mechanism of the hybrid joint at $0.21T_g$

Peel behaviour at 0.75 T_g

Localized curvature- Higher work done on the Ti alloy adherend due to strong adhesion

Inter-laminar failure of composite in the hybrid joint tested at 0.75T_g

Peel behaviour at T_g

Cohesive failure at T_g

- Adhesive breaks easily but highly dissipates the energy to create new crack surface in the adhesive bond line itself.
- Increase in temperature decreases the storage modulus and also the peak load
- High ductility of adhesive attributes to improved adhesion and cohesive failure.
- More work done on the Ti alloy-higher curvature

Peel behaviour after T_g ($1.08 T_g$, $1.25 T_g$ and $1.33 T_g$)

- Viscosity of the adhesive increases, like a semi-liquid that could not dissipate the energy effectively as in the previous cases.
- Easy bond break down and poor energy dissipation resulted cohesive failure and poor adhesion strength respectively.

Role of adhesive storage modulus in initial peel behavior

Comparison of storage modulus and initial FRP load

- Trend lines for both follow the similar pattern
- As a rule of thumb, the DMA test results could be used for debonding.
- However, joint failure modes and mechanism could not be captured.

Debonding map (1/4)

Region A

- Predominant failure mode: **Delamination**
- The flexible adherend thickness, composite fiber architecture and peel angle greatly affect the joint performance and integrity of the composite adherends
- The crack propagation entirely depends on the nucleation of initial crack; individual material system and interface energies.
- Severe damage to composite substrates and higher debonding force make **Region A unsuitable** for debonding.

Debonding map (2/4)

Region B

- Predominant failure mode: **Cohesive**
- Highest peel force of 183.5 N per 25 mm width at T_g
- After T_g , the average peel force starts to decrease drastically.
- Could not be used for practical debonding due to the uncertainties involved in the heating process and transient heat transfer nature of varying thickness of flexible adherends.
- No damage to composite substrates but **Region B suitable** for automated debonding process.

Debonding map (3/4)

Region C

- Predominant failure mode: **Cohesive**
- Above $1.17 T_g$, the joint loses most of its peel strength
- Average FRP force at $1.25 T_g$ is 94% lower when compared to T_g
- $1.17 T_g$ to $1.33 T_g$ - **most suitable region** for manual debonding and salvaging the composites without damaging

Debonding map (4/4)

Region D

- Overheating of adhesive joint might lead to affect the mechanical properties of the composite
- It may be unfit to re-introduce in service.
- **Region D** is also **unacceptable** for the thermo-mechanical debonding process.

Conclusion

- Thermo-mechanical debonding process of hybrid adhesive joints was developed.
- The bulk adhesive and adhesive joint behaviour were determined and the relation between them was analysed.
- The temperature dependent peel behaviour was used to map the suitable debonding region.
- Failure mechanisms of the hybrid joints were captured.

Debonded hybrid adhesive joint panels using thermo-mechanical debonding technique

Future work

Residual epoxy adhesive after debonding

Removal of residual adhesives using sand paper abrasion and surface reconditioning tool

Rebonded adhesive bond line with porosity- poor quality

- Surface reactivation- chemical and mechanical methods
- Rebonding strength validation